

simplest form of stripper harvesting with low intake of nongrain material in standing rice and acceptable levels of grain loss. The bulk of the straw standing in the field after stripping is unacceptable in most Chinese multi-cropping systems because it is necessary to remove the straw from the field to allow quick land preparation (1-2 d) between the first rice harvesting and second rice replanting (1-2 d).

Our work during the past 2 yr has proceeded along two lines to meet Chinese rice farmer needs. A stripper rotor placed before a reaper front (stripper-reaper system) has been fitted on a hand tractor (see figure). The appropriate distance between rotor and cutter bar is selected so the straw, after being stripped, can be cut in standing

Test results of stripper-reaper and strippercombine systems.

Item	SR-1000 system	SC-1300 system
Power (kW)	8.8	11.0
Cutting width (mm)	1000	1300
Forward speed (km h ⁻¹)	2.8-3.6	3.0-3.5
Feed rate (kg s ⁻¹)	1.1	1.3-1.4
Nongrain material (%)	12.3-17.3	3.5-4.5
Grain damage (%)	0.085	0.31
Total losses (%)	0.49-0.90	2.5-3.0
Total weight (kg)	850	1200
Estimated costs (US\$)	600	1800
Labor demand (labor-days ha ⁻¹)	4.5	2-3

position and windrowed to the side. (The stripped material feeds from stripper rotor into the tank above the reaper-front.) The engine is moved to the rear to center-balance the weight of the harvesting components. The adjust-

table skid under the engine enables the rotor to be raised or lowered, depending on crop height. Tests show that this machine has the field capacity of 1.3 ha d⁻¹ for grain harvesting and straw windrowing with grain losses less than 0.9% (see table). Estimated cost of the machine (excluding tractor) is acceptable. The wage rate of mechanical operation will be half that of the manual operation.

In 1996, we fitted a stripper rotor and conveyor on the front of a self-propelled crawler track chassis with a re-thresher and cleaner on board. The design is less labor-intensive, and is highly maneuverable in most of the wet fields in southern China. Preliminary test results of the stripper-combine system are also listed in the table. ■

Research methodology

A rapid method of isolation of genomic DNA from filamentous fungi

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This method uses fungus cultured on potato dextrose agar at 28 °C. When mat growth was visible on at least half of the plate (2-3 d), a 0.5 × 0.5 cm mycelial piece was removed with a surgical blade and placed in a 1.5-mL microfuge tube. The block was suspended in 600 µL of buffer (Tris 100 mM, pH 8.0, EDTA 150 mM, pH 8.0; NaCl 100 mM; SDS 2%; phenol 50%), and 200-300 mg of glass beads added, the contents vortexed for 3 min, and centrifuged at 13 K for 10 min. The supernatant was treated with RNase A (10-15 µg) for 15 min at 37 °C, extracted with phenol: chloroform: isoamyl alcohol (25:24:1), and the DNA precipitated with 2

volumes of absolute alcohol at room temperature. The DNA was washed with 70% alcohol and suspended in 30 µL of TE (Tris 10 mM; pH 8.0; EDTA 1 mM, pH 8.0). Genomic DNA appeared as a single, high-molecular-weight band when analyzed by a 0.8% agarose gel run in 0.5 × TBE.

To evaluate DNA prepared by this method for polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and random amplified chain, five monoconidial isolates of the rice blast fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* were analyzed. The primers used for PCR were based on the sequence of a transposable element Pot2 and the flanking target site. Two monoconidial preparations of the isolate B157 were included. The PCR was carried out in a 50-µL reaction volume of 10 mM Tris, pH 8.3; 50 mM KCl; 2.5 mM MgCl₂; 100 µM each of dATP, dCTP, dTTP, dGTP; 20 pM of each primer (17 mer); 2.5 units of Taq DNA polymerase (Perkin-Elmer); and 0.1 µg of template DNA. The thermal cyclor was programmed for 94°C, 2 min denaturation followed by 35 cycles of 94 °C 1 min; 45 °C 1 min; and 72°C 2.05 min. The final extension

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification of a part of 5'-region of Pot2, an inverted repeat transposon, using the genomic DNA of two isolates of *Magnaporthe grisea* as a template. The expected size of amplification is 0.9 kb as seen in the figure. Lanes 1 and 2 represent isolates Co1043 and B101, respectively. Lanes 3 and 4 correspond to the PCR product amplified from the DNA obtained from two separate monoconidias of isolate B101. Lanes 4 and 5 also represent isolate B101, but the DNA template used in the PCR reaction was prepared using a standard method. The last lane corresponds to the kb ladder (BRL, USA) used as a molecular weight marker.

lasted 5 min at 72 °C. The PCR products were visualized on a 1 % agarose gel run in 0.5 × TBE buffer and stained with ethidium bromide. The figure reveals amplifications of the expected size and they were identical to the DNA isolated using a standard method. DNA preparations from both the monoconidial isolates of B157 amplified the desired product, indicating reproducibility.

The yield of DNA using this method was 0.5-1.0 µg from a small sample of mycelia, which is sufficient to carry out a number of PCR and randomly amplified polymorphic DNA reactions. Employing this method of DNA extraction, we have been able to extract DNA of good quality from other filamentous fungi (*Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Phytium*, *Rhizoctonia*, and *Sclerotirzia*) that confirm its general applicability. ■

Method for detecting rice sheath blight pathogen in soil samples using mungbean

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This technique uses mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) Wilczek) as a bait plant to detect propagules of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kühn, a soilborne fungus that causes rice sheath blight. The technique involves the collection of soil samples from the field, with each sample consisting of 300-350 g (Fig. 1). Each sample is placed in pots (11 cm diam × 16 cm height) with holes for draining, and each pot filled with soil is placed inside a clean plastic bag to avoid contamination among samples during transport. Soil samples are air-dried for 10 d at 30-33 °C. Extreme temperatures, above 37-40 °C, which cause destruction of soil organisms, must be avoided. After drying to a soil moisture content of about 17-21% (w/w), each sample is then pounded to a particle size of approximately 2-5 mm in diameter and

1. Methodology for detecting *R. solani* pathogenic to rice in soil samples using mungbean seedlings.

dispensed in the original pots. Mungbean observations are done at 2- to 3-d intervals for 15 d, starting 4 d after sowing, of number of healthy plants, diseased plants, and ungerminated seeds in each pot. Seedlings infected with *R. solani* have dark brown lesions on the hypocotyl and/or cotyledons. A seedling is considered emerged when its cotyledon appears above the soil surface. Stems of infected seedlings that are more than 7 d old have dark brown lesions near the soil surface. Infected mungbean are soaked for 15 s in 5%

calcium hypochlorite, and infected tissues are cut into small sections and placed on petri dishes with potato dextrose agar (PDA) with 1 ml L⁻¹ of 25% lactic acid. After 2 d, *R. solani* colonies are again plated on PDA. Three 8-mm leaf cuts obtained from third or fourth leaves of 40- to 50-d-old IR72 are placed on water agar (0.5 g agar L⁻¹ distilled water). About 8 mm of a 4- to 5-d-old mycelial plug is placed on the center of each leaf section and incubated at 25-27 °C for 4 d to detect lesions.